

Human-Centric Based Energy and Comfort Optimization in Cognitive Buildings: A Review

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Abstract—A Cognitive Building (CB) is a cutting-edge environment that automatically adjusts its settings based on insights gained through continuous learning. These buildings employ adaptive strategies to improve security, energy efficiency, and comfort by analyzing occupant behavior, adhering to user requirements, and complying with user-defined rules. This adaptation begins with understanding how occupants use the space, including when, how, and where they occupy it. By utilizing data from different smart objects, CBs can effectively monitor and forecast user behavior, providing proactive options to enhance their experience. This paper provides a review of the most recent progress in using occupant behaviors to empower CBs to make autonomous choices, thereby enhancing security, energy efficiency, and comfort. As a novelty, it investigates how detailed information on building occupancy, including if the building is occupied, the number of people, their activity, and their precise positions within the space, could improve and optimize decision-making procedures. Furthermore, it also explores the challenges associated with the implementation of these concepts and discusses the potential future research directions that could enhance these concepts.

Index Terms—Cognitive Buildings, Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence, Occupants Behaviors, Occupancy detection, estimation, and Prediction, Activity Recognition, Occupants Localization.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Cognitive Building [1] (CB) needs to perform a variety of complex tasks to enhance the building's maintenance and efficiency, as well as the safety and comfort of its occupants, while supporting them in their day-to-day activities. Given that buildings in the EU are estimated to consume 40% of total energy¹, energy optimization is a critical issue that CBs must address [2]. Through monitoring of occupants' behaviors, CB solutions can reduce energy use and create a healthy and safe environment [3].

CBs use the Internet of Things (IoT) [4], [5] technologies to consider mutual communication among different smart objects, enabling them to work together and make autonomous decisions by monitoring their occupants' behaviors and habits

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¹Energy efficiency in buildings - European Commission - https://commission.europa.eu/news/focus-energy-efficiency-buildings-2020-02-17_en

[6]. Many studies emphasize the role of IoT devices in monitoring building surroundings and analyzing inhabitants' behaviors [7]. Such devices, which may include smart objects, wearable devices, sensors, cameras, and radars, provide extensive information about the behaviors of the occupants, such as their status, whether they are present or not, the number of occupants, the activities they are performing, and their location within the space. Monitoring and collecting this data is crucial for Artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms that analyze and predict future behaviors [8]. Knowing this will allow for efficient control of electrical appliances to operate according to these behaviors and provide the highest level of comfort, thus making buildings more cognitive. Indeed, optimizing electrical appliances, such as Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) and light systems, based on inhabitants' behaviors results in multiple advantages, including energy efficiency, improved occupant comfort, enhanced air quality, and increased resident security [9], [10].

Recent research has demonstrated that the utilization of occupancy data for HVAC management may result in considerable energy savings, with savings ranging from 10-40% [11]. Similarly, lighting systems have the potential to produce significant energy reductions of up to 75% [12]. These results show that significant energy savings have been achieved through binary occupancy detection. However, energy efficiency and occupant comfort can be further optimized by obtaining detailed information about the exact number of occupants in a space. Let's envision a scenario where we adjust a room to a comfortable 20°C temperature to accommodate five people. The heat from their bodies will raise the ambient temperature when more people enter the area. Nevertheless, the heating system continues to function under the assumption that there are only five occupants, leading to a needless elevation in temperature beyond the recommended degree of comfort. Thus, the system may persist in providing heat, resulting in excessive temporary heat and discomfort for the occupants. This not only undermines comfort but also squanders electricity while the heating system functions needlessly. In this situation, implementing a multi-occupancy detection (or better prediction) system would enable the heating system to adaptively regulate the HVAC power according to the real-time number of people present, maximizing comfort and energy efficiency. In a recent study [13], the authors proposed an approach for predicting multi-occupancy in CBs through the use of IoT technology. The proposed approach used a variety of sensors, including light, CO₂, and PIR sensors,

to collect extensive data on occupancy. In addition, a study also considered a virtual sensor that utilizes a Raspberry Pi-based touch screen to enable precise data labeling for counting occupancy. The authors use a multi-layer federated learning technique to ensure decentralized model training, protecting the occupants' privacy. The study produced encouraging outcomes, with an accuracy of 84.5% in predicting the number of multiple occupants in CBs.

Multi-occupancy prediction systems help set a desirable temperature and lighting intensity based on the number of occupants. However, recognizing that individual activities are beyond their limits. It is important to recognize these activities since occupants' needs, for temperature and lighting, are different for each activity. This can be further compounded depending on the inhabitants' priorities and comfort preferences. To address these challenges, a recent study in [14] proposed an approach for recognizing and classifying activities in smart buildings. The study highlights the importance of ultra-wideband radar technology in detecting different behaviors, especially among elderly people living in buildings. A dataset was created to verify the method. This dataset included the actions of 10 individuals engaging in 15 distinct everyday activities within a 40-square-metre flat. The dataset also included observations of movement on the opposite side of the wall. The investigation yielded satisfactory results, in which Random Forest attained an accuracy of 80%.

Apart from recognizing the activities of the inhabitants, tracking the precise location of individuals within buildings has more potential for energy and comfort optimization. Individual location tracking provides valuable insights into electrical device usage, allowing for informed decisions on which part of the electrical appliances, such as computers and printers, needs to operate and which needs to be deactivated. The study described in [15] utilized a radial basis function (RBF) network to accurately predict users' whereabouts and monitor their movements within buildings. The authors tested this localization mechanism in a benchmark smart building with an automation system to gather data and control devices. The examinations yielded highly satisfying findings, showcasing the correctness and precision of the user location data. This method provides a cost-efficient resolution for adjusting to the surrounding environment based on human presence, enabling effective energy control and enhanced comfort for occupants in intelligent building settings.

Although there have been a significant number of review articles in energy management based on occupants' behavior in buildings [10], [16], current literature has considered these topics in isolation: binary occupancy detection and prediction, multi-occupancy estimation and prediction, activity recognition, and occupant localization. These topics fall under the umbrella of occupant behaviors, which are strongly inter-correlated. As a result, these articles may not be effective enough or not consider the complete capabilities of inhabitant behaviors for energy and comfort management in buildings. This paper aims to fill this gap by thoroughly discussing all of these research topics under the umbrella topic of occupant

behavior. In addition, the study offers a concise summary of recently developed methods in each area, emphasizing their contributions and prospects for enhancing energy management strategies in intelligent buildings. By combining these topics, we aim to provide a comprehensive view of how occupants' behavior affects energy management while keeping the comfort level at a peak. Furthermore, the study also discusses in detail the potential future directions that could improve developments in decision-making for occupant comfort-based energy management in CBs through a human-centric approach.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II explains how occupant behavior could help with making autonomous decisions in CBs. Section III discusses challenges and potential future directions that could help to improve these concepts. Finally, Section IV will summarise the study's conclusions.

II. OCCUPANTS' BEHAVIOURS

Occupants' behavior refers to the habits, patterns, preferences, and interactions of inhabitants with buildings [17]. These behaviors encompass knowing about the occupancy status of space, the number of individuals, their activity, and which part of the space they occupy. Understanding and evaluating these behaviors are critical for efficient building administration, optimizing energy use, increasing occupant satisfaction, and enhancing overall building efficiency [18]. Some famous datasets have been used in the literature so far and are quickly introduced below.

- The study by Tekler et al. [19] presented a ROBOD, room-level occupancy and building operation dataset.
- The study by Kriechbaumer et al. [20] presented a global building occupant behavior database.
- The study by Dong et al. [21] presented BLOND, a building-level office environment dataset of typical electrical appliances.
- The study by Pipattanasomporn et al. [22] presented CUBEMS, smart building electricity consumption and indoor environmental sensor datasets.
- The study by Cook et al. [23] presented CASAS: A smart home in a box.

The following are significant aspects of residents' behavior that are the scope of this study.

A. Occupancy detection, estimation and prediction

Occupancy detection is the process of determining whether a space, room, or building is occupied or not. The main objective of occupancy detection is to activate or deactivate electrical appliance operations, such as controlling lighting, HVAC systems, or other building services, depending on the occupancy state, to optimize energy consumption. Occupancy estimation measures the number of people present in a particular area or building at a given time. The objective of an occupancy estimate is to provide more intricate data on occupancy levels, enabling more accurate regulation of building systems and the allocation of resources. Occupancy prediction is the process of predicting the future status or

number of occupants in a building or place by analyzing past data, patterns, or other pertinent criteria. Predicting occupancy proved useful for optimizing building management methods, such as scheduling HVAC operations using scheduling algorithms [24], controlling lighting, or planning space utilization to match projected occupancy levels.

1) *Occupancy detection and prediction:* Ghai et al. [25] propose a novel approach for detecting occupancy in commercial buildings by employing accessible context sources such as Wi-Fi access points. The authors use a cost-effective approach to collect data. After the data was collected, well-known machine learning techniques were applied. The proposed approach achieved satisfactory results with occupancy detection accuracy rates of 90%. Cali et al. [26] propose a method for detecting occupancy in indoor spaces. The author used an algorithm that is based on monitoring CO_2 levels in an indoor environment. The proposed approach was carried out in both residential and non-residential settings, including offices, sleeping or living areas, and kitchens. The study accurately detects the presence of occupants with an accuracy of 95.8%, and also estimates the actual number of inhabitants in rooms with an accuracy of 80.6%. Park et al. [27] tackle issues in building information modeling by presenting an occupancy detection system that leverages Bluetooth signals from mobile devices. The system is tested in real-world building contexts using low-cost Raspberry Pi hardware and open-source software to detect occupancy status using Bluetooth signals. The results demonstrate strong occupant recognition and effective categorization of occupancy categories without requiring occupants to install specific software, resulting in a rapid and simple deployment solution. By correctly detecting occupancy status, these systems can dynamically alter temperature and lighting levels to meet the demands and preferences of inhabitants. Khan et al. [28] employed data from various sensors to train a machine-learning model, including a Long short-term memory neural network that can retain knowledge from events that have occurred a long time in the past to predict occupancy in an office more accurately. Furthermore, to protect data privacy, the authors trained the model in a decentralized way, using federated learning. The proposed approach achieved very high results with 95% accuracy. Li et al. [29] have presented occupancy prediction inside smart buildings using an inhomogeneous Markov model for predicting occupancy presence. The proposed approach has been tested in residential buildings. The proposed approach outperforms short-term prediction, with a 5% average improvement and an 11% maximum difference in 15-minute forward predictions.

2) *Occupancy estimation and prediction:* Improving building management strategies by including occupancy estimation and prediction is a big step forward from just using binary occupancy detection. These techniques provide occupants with a more comprehensive understanding of their requirements and preferences by supplying precise data regarding the number of individuals residing in a given structure.

Chen et al. [30] introduces a novel, non-intrusive environmental sensor and a cost-effective approach for estimating

building occupancy. A conventional deep bi-directional long-short-term memory network was employed that can learn and memorize long-term relationships among the features and can learn autonomously from the data. The proposed approach accurately finds occupied spaces by combining convolutional networks with deep structures. This captures temporal dependencies in the data and considers both the past and future. According to the experimental evaluation, the proposed method is better than other methods at telling the difference between occupancy ranges (zero, low, medium, and high). Chidural et al. [31] examine three thermal imaging sensors that differ in resolution. The study focuses on characterizing the sensors, evaluating the occupancy estimation algorithms, and comparing their performance. The study presents a pipeline of unified processing algorithms for occupancy estimation, along with algorithms for data pre-processing, feature extraction, and fine-tuning. The results show that occupancy estimation is feasible for smart building applications because of its high accuracy rate of approximately 99%. Longo et al. [32] explore estimating occupancy in buildings. This method leverages management frames transmitted by users' devices over Bluetooth, WiFi, and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE). Choosing to depart from traditional methods, the suggested system offers a cost-effective and accurate solution implemented on minimally expensive hardware. By employing a supervised learning model, the system demonstrates the ability to adjust to different environments and provides estimated occupancy data to a web-based interface. Experimental findings obtained in uncontrolled outdoor and indoor environments substantiate the efficacy and dependability of the suggested solution. Through precise prediction of future occupancy levels, HVAC and illumination systems possess the capability to adapt dynamically to satisfy the requirements of occupants in real-time. Research by Khan et al. [10], [13] explored how to predict occupancy prediction in buildings that can be deployed for multi-occupancy and how it can be beneficial to minimize energy consumption and maintain comfort levels.

B. Occupant Activity Recognition

Occupant activity recognition refers to the process of identifying and comprehending the activities that inhabitants are performing in a space. It is crucial for energy management systems in buildings since occupants need, for example, different temperatures and light intensities for different activities [33]. Building systems can optimize energy efficiency and occupant comfort by correctly identifying occupant activities.

Several studies have investigated implementing activity recognition methods into energy management systems in buildings to optimally utilize important resources while efficiently ensuring occupant comfort. Fauzi et al. [34] introduce the Group Activity Recognition (GAR) technique for buildings. This system utilizes multi-image analysis from cameras to identify and track people based on their seating postures and facial features. The technique underwent testing in several circumstances, including meetings, seminars, and classroom settings. The proposed approach used a neural

network algorithm that demonstrated a learning phase accuracy of 93.33% and a testing phase accuracy of 63%, with an error rate of 37%. Ranieri et al. [35] focus on the identification of everyday activities in residential settings by using data from movies, wearable devices, and environmental sensors. The Heriot-Watt University/University of Sao Paulo (HWU-USP) activities dataset serves as the presented dataset. The datasets are available online². It contains periodic and long-term activity patterns recorded using a humanoid robot's camera and wearable and smart home sensors. Furthermore, the study employed a deep learning architecture that identifies activities through various modes of input. The HWU-USP and University of Texas at Dallas Multimodal Human Activities Dataset (UTD-MHAD) datasets have tested the framework, revealing that the inclusion of ambient sensor data significantly enhances identification accuracy. Ganesh et al. [36] introduces a technique for capturing and examining gym exercises, including push-ups, squats, planks, forward lunges, and sit-ups, using an RGB camera. The films' features were categorized using support vector machines, decision trees, K-nearest neighbors, and random forest classifiers. The models were assessed using metrics such as accuracy, balanced accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. The Random Forest classifier had the greatest level of accuracy, reaching 98.98%. All of this research produced very high accuracies by using vision-based techniques and deploying cameras for video or image-processing-based activity recognition. However, they encounter substantial privacy apprehensions since people are more concerned about the confidentiality of their data in the contemporary digital era.

Prasad et al. [37] utilized cell-phone accelerometers to recognize different human activities and employed a convolutional neural network. The proposed approach divides the data into nodes and then separates it into three primary CNN layers before the result is predicted in the output layer. The research assesses the performance of the two-dimensional CNN model in the training and testing stages, resulting in an average accuracy of 89.67%. The study emphasizes the promise of constructing efficient models using smartphone-generated information while highlighting this field's current hurdles. Peppas et al. [38] utilized a deep neural network model for real-time human activity identification utilizing tri-axial accelerometer data from mobile devices. It has two-layer convolutional neural networks and 40 statistical features that feed into a fully connected layer. The model combines feature extraction with convolutional layers. It achieves 94.18% accuracy on the WISDM dataset³ and 79.12% on the Actitracker dataset, consuming 5-8 times less storage space and providing more than twice the throughput of existing state-of-the-art approaches. While cell-phone-based activity recognition provides privacy benefits, it has drawbacks. One key difficulty is sometimes forgetting to bring phone, or the old people don't often use their phone. Furthermore, cell phones' limited

sensor coverage and background noise sensitivity might reduce activity identification algorithms' accuracy. These issues, together with concerns about battery depletion and computing power restrictions. Bouchard et al. [14] investigate the use of ultra-wideband (UWB) radar to recognize activities of daily living (ADLs) in smart homes, addressing the aforementioned problems. A dataset of 15 distinct activities was performed by 10 people in a 40-square-meter flat. With an F1-Score, the Random Forest algorithm achieved 80% accuracy. Using UWB technology for activity recognition is still in its early stages and needs further research and development. Its ability to correctly identify human activities for energy optimization and occupant comfort in buildings is promising.

C. Occupant Localization

Occupant localization refers to the determination of an individual's location or position within a building environment [39]. By using this information, building administration can better determine which parts of the space need active operation and which portions need to be deactivated.

Many studies have utilized occupant localization methods to efficiently control energy usage and improve people's comfort in buildings. Moreno et al. [40] provide a cost-effective indoor localization solution for smart buildings that tackles energy consumption issues while offering personalized services to inhabitants. The approach employs Radio frequency identification and infrared data to determine the exact position of the user. The system incorporates a radial basis function network and particle filter to accurately determine the user's location and forecast their motion. Poston et al. [41] investigate the use of naturally occurring vibration signals produced by footsteps for indoor localization. The study examined data collected from a monitored public building and assessed the suitability of traditional localization algorithms for monitoring the movement of individuals within the structure. In light of the inadequate performance of current algorithms for this task, the researchers suggest enhancements to mitigate signal distortions caused by vibrations in building structures. Wainer et al. [42] conducted a study that introduces innovative methods for indoor positioning and calculating the number of people in a building. These strategies utilize the progress made in 5G ultra-dense networks (UDNs). The method of establishing a fingerprinting database entails collecting Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) data from user equipment (UEs). Afterward, the authors use machine learning methods to predict the locations of user equipment (UEs) based on the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) values. The study approaches occupant detection as a problem of classifying between two categories, using a range of machine learning methods to construct models that estimate the count of occupants. In addition, the study uses user localization to estimate the number of people occupying specific areas of the building. The simulation findings clearly show that UDNs are very successful in accurately determining the location of individuals within and estimating the number of occupants, both in general and within specific portions of a structure. Hu et al. [43]

²Data Sets available at - <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.v6wvpzgsj>

³Data Sets available at - <https://www.cis.fordham.edu/wisdm/dataset.php>

conducted recent research that introduces a novel method using deep learning techniques to improve the accuracy of building occupancy detection and precise location determination via CCTV camera footage analysis. The study specifically develops a dual-component deep-learning model to identify the number of individuals and determine their positions in video footage. The first module utilizes a deep convolutional neural network to extract features. It performs residual and multi-branch convolutional computations to extract shallow and semantic features. Additionally, it constructs feature pyramids using a bidirectional feature network. The second module employs a three-stage detection approach using three consecutive and uniform detectors, each with progressively higher intersection over union criteria. Empirical tests conducted on CCTV recordings from a university building evaluate the detection performance of the suggested approach. The results demonstrate a higher level of performance when compared to the baseline models, emphasizing the efficacy of the suggested deep-learning-based method for detecting building occupancy. Nosrati et al. [44] presents an innovative localization system that utilizes ultra-wideband (UWB) sensors positioned externally to buildings. The proposal used two approaches to mitigate range errors induced by multipath components: one involves the use of machine learning algorithms (MLP and SVM), while the other utilizes deep learning techniques (MLP and CNNs). The simulation results are satisfactory compared to those of the conventional approach.

III. CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

Indeed, implementing occupant behavior-based control of electrical appliances provides numerous advantages, including security, energy, and comfort optimization in CBs. However, the implementation of these methods could have several challenges. These methods may require significant amounts of data to train machine learning models effectively. Often, there needs to be more data, or residents may be willing to collect their data to improve building management, but they are still worried about privacy concerns. The following are the future research directions that could be explored to investigate the potential of occupant behavior for energy and comfort management in buildings fully.

A. Privacy Preserving Solution

Advances in smart objects, including sensors, wearable devices, and radar technologies, have made it possible to generate large amounts of data while safeguarding data privacy. However, playing with this sensitive data still presents substantial difficulty due to privacy issues, especially if the data is processed in the cloud. Effectively addressing these privacy challenges is crucial in the current digital era, as individuals place a high value on privacy. One interesting method to address this privacy problem in smart buildings is to investigate decentralized learning approaches. Federated learning is a decentralized approach that allows machine learning models to be trained directly on edge devices, avoiding sending data to a central cloud server for training [45]. This

technique guarantees that sensitive data remains locally and is not exposed to the cloud, protecting inhabitants' privacy. Some papers in the literature, such as [10], [13], used FL to train their models on edge nodes instead of sending all the data to the cloud. To make FL stronger from a privacy point of view, there are many privacy mechanisms, such as differential privacy [46] and k-anonymity [47], which enforce FL with different privacy guarantees. Another method used in the literature is to take advantage of blockchain technology; one can encrypt the data and process it on a decentralized ledger, ensuring only authorized access through secure, permission-based smart contracts [48]. All of these approaches are privacy-preserving approaches that are rapidly developing research areas with tremendous potential. Researchers may use edge computing and distributed learning to create robust and privacy-conscious systems that allow inhabitants to reap the advantages of smart building technology while protecting their privacy rights in the digital age.

B. Transfer Learning

Collecting data in a building to train models can be challenging at certain times, specifically when the building was built recently, and the sensors have not yet been installed or because of resource constraints or privacy concerns. In this case, the application of transfer learning provides a very good solution. Transfer learning entails adapting pre-trained models' knowledge to similar tasks or domains and fine-tuning them on target datasets with less labelled data [49]. The transfer learning approach enables leveraging the wealth of knowledge embedded in pre-existing models trained on massive, diverse datasets. At present, the transfer learning approach is not mature yet and is considered to be a new technique in buildings with considerable promise for future research and development [50].

C. Digital Twin

Buildings account for a significant share, around 40%, of total energy use [2]. Based on this knowledge, researchers have proposed various approaches for reducing energy consumption in buildings. Among other solutions, implementing the digital twin concept offers a promising way of addressing energy consumption in the building environment. Digital twins provide a method by creating virtual replicas of real-world environments, which could potentially decrease the requirement for expensive physical installations [51]. This technique has the potential to not only improve energy use but also offer opportunities for cost savings and improved operational efficiency.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides a review of the current advancements in research that, as a novelty, considers the behaviors and habits of occupants within CBs. The study focused on several aspects of occupant's behaviors, including their occupancy status, the number of individuals present, activities, and exact location within the built environment. Understanding these behaviors

is crucial for making accurate decisions in controlling the operation of CBs, as there is a strong correlation between occupant behavior and effective building management. Furthermore, the study examines the difficulties associated with implementing these ideas and discusses in detail the possible future direction for enhancing autonomous decision-making in CBs.

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